

OUTLOOK

Visions and research directions for the Wireless World

Evaluation Report on the IMT-2020 Candidate
RIT “EUHT-5G”

WWRF WORKING GROUP D RADIO COMMUNICATIONS

White Paper
Evaluation Report for The IMT-2020 Candidate RIT “EUHT-5G”
Submitted by Nufront

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Abstract

ITU, through its committee WP5D, has conducted a process to solicit and evaluate candidate technologies that meet the requirements to be classified as part of IMT-2020. Since 2019, WWRF has been highly supportive of ITU's evaluation process for IMT-2020 and has participated as an Independent Evaluation Group (IEG). WWRF was delighted to be accepted as a Sector Member of ITU in December 2020.

The evaluation of the RIT EUHT-5G began in November 2020, with several contributions made to ITU's WP5D meetings: #37 (February 2021), #38 (June 2021), the Technology Aspects Interim Meeting (August 2021), #39 (October 2021), #41 (June 2022), and finally #42 (October 2022). Among these contributions, the final two—meeting #41 (June 2022) and meeting #42 (October 2022)—contained conclusive remarks from several IEGs, including WWRF. In our previous Outlook report, i.e. #31, we reported the outcomes of WWRF-IEG's evaluation process for the previous round of the EUHT-5G evaluation.

This report presents WWRF-IEG's contributions towards the new evaluation of EUHT-5G, which commenced in January 2024. The report is based on the results and findings of WWRF presented at ITU WP5D #48 (February 2025).

EUHT-5G is a Radio Interface Technology applicable on a large scale in fields such as high-speed railways, urban rail transit, rural household broadband coverage, and other areas. This newly proposed radio technology, EUHT-5G (Enhanced Ultra High Throughput 5G), is an ultra-high-speed wireless communication system designed to meet the requirements of high reliability, low latency, and high mobility in future mobile communication systems.

The evaluation included the KPIs of Average Spectral Efficiency, 5th Percentile Spectral Efficiency, and Connection Density. These KPIs were assessed using Link and System-Level Simulations. Several observations were reported throughout the course of the two WP5D meetings held in 2024 and 2025. To assess Average Spectral Efficiency, 5th Percentile Spectral Efficiency, and Connection Density, WWRF-IEG developed two complete in-house simulation tools, including both Link-Level and System-Level Simulators.

Based on the evaluation, it was concluded that the EUHT RIT was **NOT** able to satisfy the requirements for Average Spectral Efficiency, 5th Percentile Spectral Efficiency, and Connection Density across various configurations, as demonstrated through simulations and results presented in this report.

WWRF plans to closely follow upcoming activities within WP5D and will continue to review and provide recommendations as necessary.

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1. IMT-2020 Candidate Technology Evaluation Process

Working party 5D (WP5D) is responsible for the overall radio system aspects of International Mobile Telecommunications (IMT) systems, comprising IMT-2000, IMT-Advanced, IMT-2020 and IMT for 2030 and beyond. International Mobile Telecommunications-2020 (IMT-2020 Standard) are the requirements issued by the ITU Radiocommunication Sector (ITU-R) of the International Telecommunication Union (ITU) in 2015 for 5G networks, devices, and services.

ITU WP 5D has defined an 8-step process for preparing the IMT-2020 recommendations as shown in Figure 1-1 below.

Figure 1-1 IMT-2020 8-Step Development Process

The evaluation is based on the characteristics defined in ITU-R Reports M.2410-0, M.2411-0 and M.2412-0 using a methodology described in Report ITU-R M.2412-0. Each of these reports are briefly described in Figure 1-2:

Report ITU-R M.2410 [1]

This Report describes key requirements related to the minimum technical performance of IMT-2020 candidate radio interface technologies. It also provides the necessary background information about the individual requirements and the justification for the items and values chosen. Provision of such background information is needed for a broader understanding of the requirements. This Report is based on the ongoing development activities of external research and technology organizations.

Report ITU-R M.2411 [2]

This Report deals with on the requirements, evaluation criteria and submission templates for the development of Recommendations and Reports on IMT-2020, such as the detailed specifications of IMT 2020. It provides the service, spectrum and technical performance requirements for candidate Radio Interface Technologies (RITs)/Set of Radio Interface Technologies (SRITs) for IMT 2020.

Report ITU-R M.2412 [3]

This Report provides guidelines for the procedure, the methodology and the criteria (technical, spectrum and service) to be used in evaluating the candidate IMT-2020 radio interface technologies (RITs) or Set of RITs (SRITs) for a number of test environments. These test environments are chosen to simulate closely the more stringent radio operating environments. The evaluation procedure is designed in such a way that the overall performance of the candidate RITs/SRITs may be fairly and equally assessed on a technical basis. It ensures that the overall IMT 2020 objectives are met.

Figure 1-2 ITU-R Reports: Characteristics for Evaluation of RITs/SRITs

2. Overview of WWRF contribution in the IMT-2020 Evaluation Process

Over the past decade, WWRF has led several initiatives focused on the wireless evolution to and beyond 5G, including workshops, special sessions, presentations, white papers, and journal special issues. WWRF has actively supported the ITU’s evaluation process for IMT-2020 and participates as an independent evaluation group (IEG).

For the last five years, beginning in 2019, the IEG has been fully engaged in the WP5D IMT-2020 process for evaluation of IMT-2020 candidate technologies. The group has participated in the evaluation of 4 candidate radio interface technologies (RITs) as of today. These activities were performed:

- Initially in the context of Step 4 which was open for all submitted RITs,
- Next in the re-engagement of the evaluation (Option 2) for two specific RITs that did not receive a complete evaluation,
- In IMT-2020 submission and evaluation process for M.2150 “Revision after Year 2021”, completed in 2022.
- In Revision 3 of Recommendation ITU R M.2150, started in June 2023 and planned to complete by WP 5D meeting No. 50 (October 2025).

The evaluated technologies are listed below:

- TSDSI (IMT-2020/19)
- NUFROnt (IMT-2020/18 and IMT-2020/18(Rev1))
- ETSI (TC DECT) and DECT Forum (IMT-2020/17 and IMT-2020/17(Rev1))
- EUHT-5G (IMT-2020/75 for M.2150 “Revision after Year 2021”)
- EUHT-5G (IMT-2020/88 for M.2150 Revision 3)

The contributed material to date, related to EUHT and EUHT-5G technology and the respective WP 5D meetings is summarized in the following Table 2-1.

Table 2-1 Contributions of WWRF IEG towards IMT-2020 evaluation

Meeting	Document	Remarks
WP5D #34 (02-2020)	5D/120-E	Final evaluation report for RIT submissions From TSDSI (IMT-2020/19) and NUFROnt (IMT-2020/18)
WP5D #37 (02-2021)	5D/476	Interim evaluation report on the Candidate Technology Submission for FOR IMT-2020 “ETSI (TC DECT) and DECT Forum Proponent” As Part of the Re-engagement in Step 4 Evaluation (Report with Provisional Results).

WP5D #37 (02-2021)	5D/475	Interim evaluation report on the Candidate Technology Submission for IMT-2020 “EUHT” as part of the re-engagement in Step 4 Evaluation.
WP5D #38 (06-2021)	5D/658	Evaluation report on the Candidate Technology Submission for IMT-2020 “ETSI (TC DECT) and DECT Forum Proponent” as part of the re-engagement in Step 4 evaluation.
WP5D #38 (06-2021)	5D/659	Evaluation report on the Candidate Technology Submission for IMT-2020 “EUHT” as part of the re-engagement in Step 4 Evaluation
WG Technology Aspects Interim Meeting (08-2021)	5D/736	Updated final evaluation report on the Candidate Technology Submission for IMT-2020 “ETSI (TC DECT) and DECT Forum Proponent” as part of the re-engagement in step 4 evaluation.
WG Technology Aspects Interim Meeting (08-2021)	5D/743	Interim report based on further evaluations on the Candidate Technology Submission for IMT-2020 “EUHT technology” as part of the re-engagement in step 4 evaluation. (Final results were included subject to minor clarification from the Nufront proponent)
WP5D #39 (10-2021)	5D/760	Final report including re-evaluation of the final results for the Candidate Technology Submission for IMT-2020 “EUHT technology” as part of the re-engagement in step 4 evaluation.
WP5D #41 (06-2022)	5D/882	Interim Evaluation Report for the candidate IMT-2020 RIT “EUHT 5G” submitted by Nufront for M.2150 “Revision after year 2021”
WP5D#42 (10-2022)	5D/1061	Final evaluation report for the candidate IMT-2020 RIT “EUHT 5G” submitted by Nufront for M.2150 “revision after year 2021”
WP5D#48 (02-2025)	5D/491-E	Evaluation Report For The IMT-2020 Candidate RIT “EUHT-5G” Submitted by Nufront

The results and conclusions of these studies for the EUHT-5G RIT are presented in detail in the following sections of this Outlook. Section 3 details a short introduction of the EUHT-5G technology.

3. Introduction to the EUHT-5G Technology and Major Changes in the new RIT submission

3.1 EUHT-5G Technical Specifications and Use Case Scenarios

In this section, we introduce the proposed EUHT-5G technical specifications and discuss the use case scenarios supported by the technology. The revised technical specifications for Enhanced Ultra High Throughput 5G (EUHT-5G) were provided by **Nufront (Beijing) Technology Group Co., Ltd.** and were submitted by Nufront as a proponent to the **ITU-R** under the 'Revision After 2021' process. These technical specifications are publicly available in the document '**Enhanced Ultra High Throughput 5G (EUHT-5G) Technology Specification**', which provides an in-depth discussion of the **Medium Access Control (MAC) layer** and **physical layer** of EUHT-5G.

EUHT-5G radio interface technology is designed to operate across **both sub-6 GHz bands (450 MHz to 6000 MHz) and millimetre wave (mmWave) bands (above 24 GHz)**. The specifications introduced for EUHT-5G envision its application in supporting future wireless technologies such as **the Internet of Things (IoT) and Machine-to-Machine (M2M) networks**, among others. Additionally, the use of **mmWave bands** provides the required spectrum to support **high-capacity applications** that demand substantial bandwidth and low latency.

3.1.1 Use Case Scenarios

The proposal submitted by **Nufront** addresses three primary use cases:

1. **Enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB)**
2. **Massive Machine-Type Communications (mMTC)**
3. **Ultra-Reliable Low Latency Communication (URLLC)**

Furthermore, the proposal considers **all five test environments** outlined in **Report ITU-R M.2412-0**. The information shared by Nufront presents a vision for key enabling technologies and provides practical deployment scenarios, including **high-speed connectivity for moving trains**, which falls under the **rural eMBB** category.

EUHT-5G is designed to meet the **performance metrics** for both **uplink and downlink** transmissions. The accompanying technical document outlines the **overall system reference model**, detailing the functions of both the **MAC layer** and the **physical layer**. The MAC layer of EUHT-5G is based on a **centralised control architecture for multi-user scheduling**, optimising resource allocation and network efficiency.

3.1.2 Radio Interface Functional Aspects

The technical specifications of EUHT-5G define the **functional aspects of the radio interface** and discuss the **multiple access schemes** it utilises, which is a combination of:

- **Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiple Access (OFDMA)**
- **Time Division Multiple Access (TDMA)**
- **Space Division Multiple Access (SDMA)**

The modulation schemes for EUHT-5G are separately defined for the **sub-6 GHz band** and the **mmWave band**, ensuring optimal performance in both frequency ranges. Similarly, **channel tracking capabilities** are also distinct for each band, with different types of **reference signals** used for **uplink** and **downlink** communications.

3.1.3 Advanced Antenna Capabilities

One of the key technological aspects of EUHT-5G is its support for **advanced antenna systems**, enabling improved signal quality, coverage, and efficiency. The specifications propose **Multi-Input Multi-Output (MIMO) transmission** for both the **user device** and the **base station**. Specifically, EUHT-5G supports **between 1 and 32 antenna elements** for both uplink and downlink, with the antenna elements arranged in a **regular rectangular pattern**. Additionally, EUHT-5G proposes support for both **remote** and **distributed antenna systems**, improving network flexibility and coverage in various environments.

3.1.4 Priority Access for Emergency Services

EUHT-5G is also envisioned to support **emergency services**, such as **connected ambulances, public safety networks, and healthcare communication systems**. To facilitate this, the specification includes a mechanism for **priority access to wireless networks**, defining a range of **access control mechanisms**. The proposed technology differentiates between **normal users** and **priority users**, triggering distinct access mechanisms based on the type of service request. This ensures that critical communications, such as those related to **public safety or healthcare**, receive prioritised network access when required.

3.1.5 Support for a Wide Range of Services

EUHT-5G aims to support a **diverse set of services**, as defined in **Recommendation ITU-R M.2083**. Some of the key applications for each use case include:

eMBB (Enhanced Mobile Broadband):

- High-speed connectivity for **trains**
- **Interactive** and **broadcast services**

URLLC (Ultra-Reliable Low Latency Communication):

- **Mobile healthcare applications**
- **Smart transportation**
- **Power grid communications**

mMTC (Massive Machine-Type Communications):

- **Smart cities**
- **Smart homes**
- **Machine-to-Machine (M2M) communications**

The detailed technical specifications and deployment scenarios outlined in this outlook illustrate the potential of EUHT-5G in addressing the evolving demands of next-generation wireless communication systems.

3.2 Summary and Key changes to the new EUHT-5G specification

To the best of our knowledge and after a thorough comparison of the previous submission of EUHT-5G (Doc. [5D/979](#)), following are the major changes found in the new EUHT-5G specification ([ITU-WP5D SharePoint](#)). We have highlighted potential benefits of these changes and their associated KPIs.

- **Antenna Ports at the Base Station**

The use of up to 32 antenna ports at the base station can significantly enhance EUHT-5G performance by enabling advanced MIMO techniques. This may increase the capacity and coverage of the network, providing **higher data rates** and **improved reliability**.

- **Higher Modulation Schemes**

Implementing up to 4096-QAM can allow EUHT-5G networks to transmit **more bits per symbol (may improve spectral efficiency)**, hence positively impacting the spectral efficiency. This higher modulation order increases the data throughput, making more efficient use of the available spectrum. *However, it requires a higher SNR to maintain signal quality, making it most effective only in areas with excellent signal conditions.*

- **Supporting more sub-Channels in a single component carrier**

Based on the new EUHT-5G specification, the network can support up to 10 sub-channels within a single component carrier. This granularity may allow for more flexible and **efficient spectrum use (may enhance spectral efficiency)**, enabling the network to serve multiple users with **varying bandwidth requirements** simultaneously and adaptively improving the **network capacity**.

- **Flexible Carrier Aggregation (CA)**

Carrier aggregation in the revised EUHT-5G is more flexible, allowing the combination of multiple frequency bands to increase the total available bandwidth. This flexibility may allow using non-contiguous spectrum efficiently and provide **higher peak data rates**.

- **Detailed Description of Handovers**

The EUHT-5G revision provides more detailed procedures for network joining and handover for seamless connectivity and **minimal interruption** when users move between different cells.

- **More Flexible Phase Tracking Pilots**

Flexible phase tracking pilots in the new EUHT-5G specification can help maintain accurate synchronisation of the signal phase between the transmitter and receiver, even in challenging

environments. This may support **high mobility** with greater signal quality and also may improve **reliability**.

- **More Reliable Preambles in Low Error Mode**

EUHT-5G revision employs more reliable preambles, especially in low error mode, which improves the accuracy of initial access and synchronisation processes. This may enhance **reliability**.

- **More MCSs in Low Error Mode**

The introduction of more Modulation and Coding Schemes (MCSs) in low error mode may allow EUHT-5G to adapt more precisely to varying signal conditions. This flexibility optimises the trade-off between data rate and error resilience, providing a more stable and **reliable** connection, particularly in environments with fluctuating signal quality (such as the cell-edge).

- **Overall, more MCSs**

EUHT-5G revision introduces a wider range of MCSs for control channels and signalling/feedback channels. This enhancement improves the network **efficiency and reliability**.

4. EUHT-5G RIT Evaluation

4.1 Background

The proposal and technical specifications of EUHT-5G are documented in the following material listed in Table 4-1:

Table 4-1 EUHT-5G Technology Proposal and technical specification to IMT-2020

Meeting number	Input contributions	Remarks
WP 5D #45	<p>5D/51 (Attachment Part 1: 5D/51!P1; Attachment Part 2: 5D/51!P2; Attachment Part 3: 5D/51!P3; Attachment Part 4: 5D/51!P4; Attachment Part 5: 5D/51!P5); Attachment Part 6: 5D/51!P6);</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Final submission • Characteristics template • Compliance template • Link budget template • Self-evaluation report • EUHT-5G specification • EUHT-5G specification change records

4.2 Methodology

The technical performance requirements listed in the table below have been assessed (Ref: Report ITU-R M.2412-0). In this Table we list for each addressed characteristic the assessment method used (based on ITU evaluation methodology), references to the requirements and exact methodology steps from corresponding ITU documents M.2410-0 and M.2412-0.

Table 4-2 KPIs evaluated and presented in this report

Characteristic for evaluation (test-environment)	High-level assessment method	Reference to M.2410-0 Requirements Document	Reference to M.2412-0 Evaluation Document
5 th Percentile Spectral Efficiency	Simulation	§ 4.4	§ 7.1.2
Average Spectral Efficiency	Simulation	§ 4.5	§ 7.1.1
Connection density (mMTC)	Simulation	§ 4.8	§ 7.1.3

For evaluating the KPIs based on simulation (Average and 5th percentile spectral efficiency & Connection Density) we developed independent simulation tools from scratch with the help of EUHT-5G technical specifications. Two end-to-end Physical Layer simulators of the EUHT-5G

technology were developed by WWRF IEG. These simulators were able to perform jointly system-level and link-level experiments. As per the ITU requirements [3], Average and 5th percentile spectral efficiency, and connection density KPIs are evaluated using both the link-level and system-level simulations. Our developed simulation tools were based on two main components defined in Figure 4-1 as follows.

Figure 4-1 Breakdown of the EUHT Simulation tool

WWRF IEG developed system-level simulators that are able to take into account the specifications of the EUHT-5G RIT, while remaining aligned with the evaluation guidelines defined in ITU-R M.2412-0 [3] which are shown in Figure 4-2 and Figure 4-4 for both KPIs.

7.1.1 Average spectral efficiency

Let $R_i(T)$ denote the number of correctly received bits by user i ($i = 1, \dots, N$) (downlink) or from user i (uplink) in a system comprising a user population of N users and M Transmission Reception Points (TRxPs). Further, let W denote the channel bandwidth and T the time over which the data bits are received. The average spectral efficiency may be estimated by running system-level simulations over number of drops N_{drops} . Each drop gives a value of $\sum_{i=1}^N R_i(T)$ denoted as:

$R^{(1)}(T), \dots, R^{(N_{drops})}(T)$ and the estimated average spectral efficiency resulting is given by:

$$\widehat{SE}_{avg} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^{N_{drops}} R^{(j)}(T)}{N_{drops} T.W.M} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^{N_{drops}} \sum_{i=1}^N R_i^{(j)}(T)}{N_{drops} T.W.M}$$

where \widehat{SE}_{avg} is the estimated average spectral efficiency and will approach the actual average with an increasing number of N_{drops} and $R_i^{(j)}(T)$ is the simulated total number of correctly received bits for user i in drop j .

The average spectral efficiency is evaluated by system level simulation using the evaluation configuration parameters of Indoor Hotspot-eMBB, Dense Urban-eMBB, and Rural-eMBB test environments as defined in this Report. It should be noted that the average spectral efficiency is evaluated only using a single-layer layout configuration even if a test environment comprises a multi-layer layout configuration.

The results from the system-level simulation are used to derive the average spectral efficiency as defined in Report ITU-R M.2410-0. The necessary information is the number of correctly received bits per UE during the active session time the UE is in the simulation. The effective bandwidth is the operating bandwidth normalized appropriately considering the uplink/downlink ratio for TDD system.

Layer 1 and Layer 2 overheads should be accounted for in time and frequency. Examples of Layer 1 overhead include synchronization, guard band and DC subcarriers, guard/switching time (for example, in TDD systems), pilots and cyclic prefix. Examples of Layer 2 overhead include common control channels, HARQ ACK/NACK signalling, channel feedback, random access, packet headers and CRC. It must be noted that in computing the overheads, the fraction of the available physical resources used to model control overhead in Layer 1 and Layer 2 should be accounted for in a non-overlapping way. Power allocation/boosting should also be accounted for in modelling resource allocation for control channels.

Figure 4-2 IMT-2020 guidelines for evaluation of Avg. Spectral Efficiency

7.1.2 5th percentile user spectral efficiency

5th percentile user spectral efficiency is the 5th percentile point of the cumulative distribution function (CDF) of the normalized user throughput, estimated from all possible user locations.

Let user i in drop j correctly decode $R_i^{(j)}(T)$ accumulated bits in $[0, T]$. For non-scheduled duration of user i zero bits are accumulated. During this total time user i receives accumulated service time of $T_i \leq T$, where the service time is the time duration between the first packet arrival and when the last packet of the burst is correctly decoded. In case of full buffer, $T_i = T$. Hence the rate normalised by service time T_i and channel bandwidth W of user i in drop j , $r_i^{(j)}$, is:

$$r_i^{(j)} = \frac{R_i^{(j)}(T)}{T_i W}$$

Running N_{drops} simulations leads to $N_{drops} \times N$ values of $r_i^{(j)}$ of which the lowest 5th percentile point of the CDF is used to estimate the 5th percentile user spectral efficiency.

The 5th percentile user spectral efficiency is evaluated by system level simulation using the evaluation configuration parameters of Indoor Hotspot-eMBB, Dense Urban-eMBB, and Rural-eMBB test environments. It should be noted that the 5th percentile user spectral efficiency is evaluated only using a single-layer layout configuration even if a test environment comprises a multi-layer layout configuration. The 5th percentile user spectral efficiency shall be evaluated using identical simulation assumptions as the average spectral efficiency for that test environment.

The results from the system-level simulation are used to derive the 5th percentile user spectral efficiency as defined in Report ITU-R M.2410-0. The necessary information is the number of correctly received bits per UE during the active session time the UE is in the simulation. The effective

bandwidth is the operating bandwidth normalized appropriately considering the uplink/downlink ratio for TDD system.

Layer 1 and Layer 2 overheads should be accounted for in time and frequency. Examples of Layer 1 and Layer 2 overheads can be found in § 7.1.1 for average spectral efficiency.

Figure 4-3 IMT-2020 guidelines for evaluation of 5th Percentile Spectral Efficiency

7.1.3 Connection density

There are two possible evaluation methods to evaluate connection density requirement defined in ITU-R M.2410-0:

- non-full buffer system-level simulation;
- full-buffer system-level simulation followed by link-level simulation.

The following steps are used to evaluate the connection density based on non-full buffer system-level simulation. Traffic model used in this method is defined in Table 8-2 in § 8.4 of this Report.

Step 1: Set system user number per TRxP as N .

Step 2: Generate the user packet according to the traffic model.

Step 3: Run non-full buffer system-level simulation to obtain the packet outage rate. The outage rate is defined as the ratio of the number of packets that failed to be delivered to the destination receiver within a transmission delay of less than or equal to 10s to the total number of packets generated in *Step 2*.

Step 4: Change the value of N and repeat *Step 2-3* to obtain the system user number per TRxP N' satisfying the packet outage rate of 1%.

Step 5: Calculate connection density by equation $C = N' / A$, where the TRxP area A is calculated as $A = \text{ISD}^2 \times \text{sqrt}(3)/6$, and ISD is the inter-site distance.

The requirement is fulfilled if the connection density C is greater than or equal to the connection density requirement defined in Report ITU-R M.2410-0.

The simulation bandwidth used to fulfill the requirement should be reported. Additionally, it is encouraged to report the connection efficiency (measured as N' divided by simulation bandwidth) for the achieved connection density.

Step 6: Calculate the number of supported connections per TRxP, $N = W / \text{mean}(B_i)$. W is the simulation bandwidth. The mean of B_i may be taken over the best 99% of the $SINR_i$ conditions.

- In case UE multiplexing is modelled in *Step 1*, $N = N_{\text{mux}} \times W / \text{mean}(B_i)$. In case UE multiplexing is modelled in *Step 2*, $N = W / \text{mean}(B_i/n_{\text{mux},i})$.

Step 7: Calculate the connection density as $C = N / A$, where the TRxP area A is calculated as $A = \text{ISD}^2 \times \text{sqrt}(3)/6$, and ISD is the inter-site distance.

The requirement is fulfilled if the 99th percentile of the delay per user D_i is less than or equal to 10s, and the connection density is greater than or equal to the connection density requirement defined in Report ITU-R M.2410-0.

The simulation bandwidth used to fulfill the requirement should be reported. Additionally, it is encouraged to report the connection efficiency (measured as N divided by simulation bandwidth) for the achieved connection density.

Figure 4-4 IMT-2020 Guidelines for evaluation of RITs (Connection Density-mMTC)

4.3 SPECTRAL EFFICIENCY: Channel Modelling, Link, and system-level simulations

4.3.1 Channel Model used in the simulations

The channel model utilised in this study is based on the **3GPP TR 38.901** [1] implementation of a channel model [2][3]. This is a **three-dimensional (3D) statistical Spatial Channel Model (SCM)** designed to support various **propagation environments**, including **urban, rural, and indoor scenarios**. Additionally, it accommodates **multi-antenna operations** and provides a framework for modelling **wireless channels** across a frequency range of **0.5 GHz to 100 GHz**.

The implementation specifically focused on the following key aspects:

- **Path loss and shadowing models** (as defined in **3GPP TR 38.901, Section 7.4.1**)
- **Autocorrelation characteristics of shadow fading** (as detailed in **3GPP TR 38.901, Section 7.4.4**)
- **Channel condition models**, covering different fading and propagation conditions (**3GPP TR 38.901, Section 7.4.2**)

To validate the accuracy of our channel model, we conducted a comparative analysis between the **3GPP TR 38.901 specification** and the **IMT-2020 channel specification**. After careful examination, we identified only a few **minor parameter variations**, which were determined to have **negligible to no impact** on the overall simulation results. As a result, we proceeded with the development of the **EUHT channel model** based on the **3GPP channel framework**.

Figure 4-5 Channel coefficient generation procedure

4.3.2 Evaluation of EUHT in terms of Average and 5th Percentile Spectral Efficiency

4.3.3 5th Percentile Spectral Efficiency:

According to Report ITU-R M.2410 [1], the 5th percentile user spectral efficiency represents the value at the 5% point of the cumulative distribution function (CDF) of normalised user throughput. This normalised user throughput is calculated as the number of correctly received bits (i.e., the bits in the Service Data Units (SDUs) delivered to Layer 3) over a specific period, divided by the channel bandwidth, and is expressed in bit/s/Hz.

ITU-R M.2412 [3] mandates that the 5th percentile user spectral efficiency be evaluated alongside the average spectral efficiency using the **same simulation**. Consequently, the evaluation results for the 5th percentile user spectral efficiency are presented together with the average spectral efficiency in Section II-D-1 and II-D-2 of this report.

4.3.4 Average Spectral Efficiency:

As outlined in Report ITU-R M.2410 [1], average spectral efficiency is calculated by taking the total throughput of all users (the number of correctly received bits, i.e., the bits in the Service Data Units (SDUs) delivered to Layer 3, over a given period) and dividing it by the channel bandwidth of a specific band, then further dividing by the number of TRxPs. This metric is expressed in bit/s/Hz/TRxP.

Report ITU-R M.2412 [3] stipulates that average spectral efficiency and 5th percentile user spectral efficiency must be evaluated together using the same simulation. For EUHT-5G, both average spectral efficiency and 5th percentile user spectral efficiency are assessed, considering a variety of antenna configurations and transmission schemes.

4.3.5 Link Level Simulator Design and Simulations:

Transmitter Design:

The detailed transmitter design for Downlink and Uplink are shown in Figure 4-6 and Figure 4-7.

Figure 4-6 Transmitter Design for EUHT technology (CAP side)

Figure 4-7 Uplink Transmitter Design for EUHT technology (STA side)

Link level Simulator Design:

Define

- Define Simulation Parameters:
 - Set up the channel bandwidth, modulation schemes, coding rates, and other physical layer parameters.
 - Define the channel model (Section II-C-1-C)

Generate

- Generate Channel Realisations:
 - Create multiple instances of the channel model to simulate different channel conditions e.g., half/full buffer
 - Include parameters e.g., path loss, shadowing, and multipath fading.

Transmit

- Transmit Data:
 - Simulate the transmission of data packets through the channel.
 - Apply different MCSs.

Receive

- Receive Data:
 - Simulate the reception of data packets at the receiver.
 - Include channel estimation, equalisation, and decoding processes.

Calculate

- Calculate Throughput:
 - Measure the number of correctly received bits over the simulation period.
 - Normalise the throughput by the channel bandwidth to obtain spectral efficiency (bit/s/Hz).

Repeat

- Repeat for Multiple Realisations:
 - Run the simulation for a large number of channel realisations to gather statistical data.

The link-level and system-level simulators work together to provide a comprehensive evaluation of network performance. The link-level simulator focuses on the physical layer, simulating the transmission and reception of data packets under various channel conditions to determine the spectral efficiency for individual links. This involves detailed modelling of modulation, coding, channel estimation, and decoding processes. The system-level simulator, on the other hand, considers the entire network layout, including the distribution of users, resource allocation, and interference management. It aggregates the results from multiple link-level simulations to evaluate overall network performance metrics such as average spectral efficiency and 5th percentile user spectral efficiency. By combining the detailed physical layer insights from the link-level simulator with the broader network-level analysis from the system-level simulator, a holistic understanding of the network's capabilities and performance is achieved. This integrated approach ensures that both individual link performance and overall network efficiency are accurately assessed as per the guidelines in [3].

Figure 4-8 19-Cell scenario with 3 sites per cell (57 sites)

System level Simulator Design:

Define Network Layout:

- Set up the network topology, 19 cell scenario, total 57 sites.

User Distribution:

- Randomly distribute users.
- Assign users to cells based on signal strength (10 devices per cell i.e., 570 devices)

Channel Assignment:

- Assign channel conditions to each user based on their location and the channel model.

Traffic Model:

- Define the traffic model for user data generation (full-buffer).
- Simulate the arrival and departure of data packets.

Resource Allocation:

- Implement the scheduling algorithm to allocate resources

Simulate Data Transmission:

- Simulate the transmission and reception of data packets for all users.
- Include interference from neighbouring cells and other users.

Calculate Average and 5th Percentile Spectral Efficiency:

- Measure the total throughput for all users and normalise by the channel bandwidth and number of TRxPs to obtain average spectral efficiency (bit/s/Hz/TRxP).
- Calculate the 5th percentile user spectral efficiency by finding the 5% point of the cumulative distribution function (CDF) of user throughputs.

Repeat:

- Run the simulation for multiple user distributions to gather statistical data.

4.3.6 Simulation parameters and technical assumptions for Indoor eMBB

Following are the simulation parameters used in the link and system level simulations for evaluating average and 5th percentile spectral efficiency Indoor hotspot scenario.

Table 4-3 Simulation Parameters and Assumptions (Link and System Level) for Indoor Hotspot

Indoor Hotspot - eMBB		Configuration A
Carrier frequency for evaluation		4 GHz
BS antenna height		3 m
Transmit power per TRxP		21 dBm for 10MHz bandwidth
Inter-site distance		20m
BS noise figure		5 dB
UE noise figure		7 dB
Device deployment		100% indoor
UE speeds of interest		3 km/h (Indoor)
Traffic model		Full buffer
Simulation bandwidth		10MHz
UE density		10 UEs per TRxP
UE antenna height		1.5m
Channel model variant		Channel model A
Handover margin (dB)		0
Antenna Configuration and Parameters		
Number of antenna elements per TRxP		32Tx/Rx
Number of TXRU per TRxP		32TXRU
Number of UE antenna elements		4Tx/Rx
Number of TXRU per UE		4TXRU
BS antenna element gain		5dBi
UE antenna element gain		0 dBi
UE antenna element pattern		Omni-directional
Mechanic tilt		180° in GCS
Electronic tilt		90° in LCS
TRxP number per site		1

Table 4-4 Simulation Parameters for the PHY layer – Indoor Hotspot

Parameters	Values
Modulation	Up to 4096 QAM
Channel Coding	LDPC
Multiple access	OFDMA
Duplexing	TDD
Subcarrier Spacing	78.125 KHz
Simulation bandwidth	20 MHz
Transmission Scheme	DL: SU/MU-MIMO, UL: SU-MIMO
Frame structure	DL:UL = 2:1
Antenna configuration at TRxP	32Tx, (16,4,2,1,1;4,4)
Antenna configuration at UE	8Rx, (1,4,2,1,1;1,4)
Scheduling	Proportional Fairness (PF)
Receiver	MMSE-IRC
Channel estimation	Non-ideal (as per Nufront's SER)

4.3.7 Simulation parameters and technical assumptions for Dense Urban Macro

Following are the simulation parameters used in the link and system level simulations for evaluating average and 5th percentile spectral efficiency Dense Urban Macro scenario.

Table 4-5 Simulation Parameters and Assumptions (Link and System Level) for Urban Macro

Urban Macro - eMBB	Configuration A
Carrier frequency for evaluation	4 GHz
BS antenna height	25 m
Total transmit power per TRxP	41 dBm for 10MHz bandwidth
Inter-site distance	200m
BS noise figure	5 dB
UE noise figure	7 dB
Device deployment	80% indoor and 20% Outdoor
UE speeds of interest	3 km/h (Indoor) and 30 km/h Outdoor
Traffic model	Full buffer
Simulation bandwidth	10MHz
UE density	10 UEs per TRxP
UE antenna height	1.5m Outdoor Users
Channel model variant	Channel model A
Handover margin (dB)	0

Antenna Configuration and Parameters	
Number of antenna elements per TRxP	128 Tx/Rx
Number of TXRU per TRxP	4 TXRU
Number of UE antenna elements	4 Tx/Rx
Number of TXRU per UE	4 TXRU
BS antenna element gain	8 dBi
UE antenna element gain	0 dBi
UE antenna element pattern	Omni-directional
Mechanic tilt	90° in GCS
TRxP number per site	3

Table 4-6 Simulation Parameters for the PHY layer –Dense Urban

Parameters	Values
Modulation	Up to 4096 QAM
Channel Coding	LDPC
Multiple access	OFDMA
Duplexing	TDD
Subcarrier Spacing	78.125 KHz
Simulation bandwidth	20 MHz
Transmission Scheme	DL: SU/MU-MIMO, UL: SU-MIMO
Frame structure	DL:UL = 2:1
Antenna configuration at TRxP	32Tx, (16,4,2,1,1;4,4)
Antenna configuration at UE	8Rx, (1,4,2,1,1;1,4)
Scheduling	Proportional Fairness (PF)
Receiver	MMSE-IRC
Channel estimation	Non-ideal (as per Nufont's SER)

4.4 Results for Average and 5th Percentile Spectral Efficiency

4.4.1 Average & 5th Percentile Spectral Efficiency for Indoor-Hotspot Downlink and Uplink

Downlink:

Figure 4-9 CDF for Downlink SE from System-Level simulations (Indoor Hotspot)

Based on the CDF curve above, the evaluation results of DL spectral efficiency for EUHT-5G for evaluation configuration A are provided in Table 7. It is observed that EUHT-5G does not fulfill the DL spectral efficiency requirement for eMBB in Indoor Hotspot test environment.

Table 4-7 Results for DL Indoor Hotspot, Configuration A

Minimum technical performance requirements (ITU-R M.2410)	Category			Required value	Value	Meets the Requirement ?	Remarks
	Usage scenario	Test environment	Downlink or Uplink				
Average Spectral Efficiency (bits/s/Hz/TRxP)	eMBB	Indoor Hotspot	Downlink	9	6.31	No	Does not meet the criteria for DL for both KPIs.
5 th Percentile Spectral Efficiency (bits/s/Hz)				0.30	0.2	No	

Uplink:

Figure 4-10 CDF for Uplink SE from System-Level simulations (Indoor Hotspot)

Based on the CDF curve above, the evaluation results of UL spectral efficiency for EUHT-5G for evaluation configuration A are provided in Table 8. It is observed that EUHT-5G does not fulfill the UL spectral efficiency requirement for eMBB in Indoor Hotspot test environment.

Table 4-8 Results for UL Indoor Hotspot, Configuration A

Minimum technical performance requirements (ITU-R M.2410)	Category			Required value	Value	Meets the Requirement ?	Remarks
	Usage scenario	Test environment	Downlink or Uplink				
Average Spectral Efficiency (bits/s/Hz/TRxP)	eMBB	Indoor Hotspot	Uplink	6.75	3.88	No	Does not meet the criteria for DL for both KPIs. Observations in Section II-D-3.
5 th Percentile Spectral Efficiency (bits/s/Hz)				0.21	0.11	No	

4.4.2 Average & 5th Percentile Spectral Efficiency for Dense Urban Downlink and Uplink

Downlink:

Figure 4-11 CDF for Downlink SE from System-Level simulations (Dense Urban Macro)

Based on the CDF curve above, the evaluation results of DL spectral efficiency for EUHT-5G for evaluation configuration A (Dense Urban test environment) are provided in Table 9. It is observed that EUHT-5G does not fulfill the DL spectral efficiency requirement for eMBB in dense urban test environment.

Table 4-9 Results for DL eMBB Dense Urban Macro, Configuration A

Minimum technical performance requirements (ITU-R M.2410)	Category			Required value	Value	Meets the Requirement ?	Remarks
	Usage scenario	Test environment	Downlink or Uplink				
Average Spectral Efficiency (bits/s/Hz/TRxP)	eMBB	Dense Urban	Downlink	7.8	4.644	No	Does not meet the criteria for DL for both KPIs. Observations in Section II-D-3.
5 th Percentile Spectral Efficiency (bits/s/Hz)				0.225	0.13	No	

Uplink:

Figure 4-12 CDF for Uplink SE from System-Level simulations (Dense Urban Macro)

Based on the CDF curve above, the evaluation results of UL spectral efficiency for EUHT-5G for evaluation configuration A are provided in Table 10. It is observed that EUHT-5G does not fulfill the UL spectral efficiency requirement for eMBB in dense urban test environment.

Table 4-10 Results for UL Dense Urban Macro, Configuration A

Minimum technical performance requirements (ITU-R M.2410)	Category			Required value	Value	Meets the Requirement ?	Remarks
	Usage scenario	Test environment	Downlink or Uplink				
Average Spectral Efficiency (bits/s/Hz/TRxP)	eMBB	Dense Urban	Uplink	5.4	3.07	No	Does not meet the criteria for DL for both KPIs. Observations in Section II-D-3.
5 th Percentile Spectral Efficiency (bits/s/Hz)				0.15	0.09	No	

4.4.3 Observations from the results for Spectral Efficiency

While simulating spectral efficiency for various MCSs and Antennae configurations, following observations were made by the IEG.

4.4.3.1 Observation 1: Low Error Mode and Spectral Efficiency

Low Error Mode: This mode does not support Multi-User Multiple Input Multiple Output (MU-MIMO), which is a technique that allows multiple users to be served simultaneously using the same frequency resources.

Impact on Spectral Efficiency: Without MU-MIMO, the cell can only use Frequency Division Multiplexing (FDM) to serve users, which is less efficient. This results in lower spectral efficiency.

Reason for Switching to Low Error Mode: The cell switches to this mode when the channel conditions are poor, specifically when the Signal-to-Interference-plus-Noise Ratio (SINR) of the scheduled users is less than -11 dB (as per section 1.7.1.1 of the EUHT-5G specification).

Modulation Constraints: Under these poor conditions, higher-order modulations like 16QAM or 64QAM CANNOT be used. These modulations are typically used when the SINR is high, allowing for more bits to be transmitted per symbol.

4.4.3.2 Observation 2: Low SINR and Channel Estimation

Low SINR at Cell Edges: Users at the edge of the cell experience low SINR, which affects the accuracy of channel estimation.

Degraded Data Channel Performance: Poor channel estimation leads to errors in the data channel.

Repetition and Spectral Efficiency: MCS 124 and MCS 125 introduce repetition in data transmission to improve reliability, but this repetition reduces spectral efficiency because the same data is transmitted multiple times, consuming more bandwidth.

4.4.3.3 Observation 3: SICH/CCH Transmission and Beamforming

SICH/CCH Transmission: The System Information Channel (SICH) and Control Channel (CCH) are transmitted across the entire cell coverage area.

Lack of Beamforming Gain: Unlike the data channel, these channels DO NOT benefit from beamforming, which focuses the signal in a specific direction to improve signal strength and quality.

Issues at Cell Edges: For users at the cell edges, the SICH/CCH faces SIMILAR channel estimation issues as the data channel, leading to degraded performance.

4.5 CONNECTION DENSITY

4.5.1 ITU Requirement & Evaluation methodology

4.5.1.1 Minimum requirement

Connection density represents the total number of devices fulfilling a specific quality of service (QoS) per unit area (per km²) as defined in ITU-R M.2410-0. The target QoS is to support delivery of a message of a certain size within a certain time and with a certain

probability of success, as specified in ITU-R M.2412-0. This requirement is defined for the purpose of evaluation in the mMTC usage scenario. The minimum requirement for connection density is 1 000 000 devices per km², which should be achieved with a maximum delay of 10s and success probability of at least 99%.

4.5.1.2 Evaluation Methodology

Connection density is evaluated through simulation. The system simulation methodology for the connection density KPI evaluation is detailed in M.2412. The methodology details two options:

- Non-full buffer system-level simulation.
- Full-buffer system-level simulation followed by link-level simulation.

In our evaluation study, we have applied the full buffer approach. The generic steps described in M.2412 are the following:

- Step 1:** Perform full-buffer system-level simulation using the evaluation parameters for Urban Macro-mMTC test environment, determine the uplink $SINR_i$ for each percentile $i=1\dots99$ of the distribution over users, and record the average allocated user bandwidth W_{user} .
- In case UE multiplexing on the same time/frequency resource is modelled in this step, record the average number of multiplexed users N_{mux} . $N_{mux} = 1$ for no UE multiplexing.
- Step 2:** Perform link-level simulation and determine the achievable user data rate R_i for the recorded $SINR_i$ and W_{user} values.
- In case UE multiplexing on the same time/frequency resource is modelled in this step, record the average number of multiplexed users $n_{mux,i}$ under $SINR_i$. The achievable data rate for this case is derived by $R_i = Z_i/n_{mux,i}$, where aggregated bit rate Z_i is the summed bit rate of $n_{mux,i}$ users on W_{user} . $n_{mux,i} = 1$ for no UE multiplexing.
- Step 3:** Calculate the packet transmission delay of a user as $D_i = S/R_i$, where S is the packet size.
- Step 4:** Calculate the traffic generated per user as $T = S/T_{inter-arrival}$, where $T_{inter-arrival}$ is the inter-packet arrival time.
- Step 5:** Calculate the long-term frequency resource requested under $SINR_i$ as $B_i = T/(R_i/W_{user})$.

Step 6: Calculate the number of supported connections per TRxP, $N = W / \text{mean}(B_i)$. W is the simulation bandwidth. The mean of B_i may be taken over the best 99% of the $SINR_i$ conditions.

- In case UE multiplexing is modelled in *Step 1*, $N = N_{\text{mux}} \times W / \text{mean}(B_i)$. In case UE multiplexing is modelled in *Step 2*, $N = W / \text{mean}(B_i/n_{\text{mux},i})$.

Step 7: Calculate the connection density as $C = N / A$, where the TRxP area A is calculated as $A = \text{ISD}^2 \times \text{sqrt}(3)/6$, and ISD is the inter-site distance.

The requirement is fulfilled if the 99th percentile of the delay per user D_i for a packet size of 32 bytes is less than or equal to 10s, and the connection density is greater than or equal to 1 000 000 devices.

4.5.1.3 Test Environments and Configurations

Connection Density is relevant for the massive machine type communications (mMTC) usage scenario (M.2412 - §8.1). This usage scenario is characterized by a very large number of connected devices typically transmitting a relatively low volume of non-delay-sensitive data.

Connection Density should be assessed in an urban macro (Urban Macro–mMTC) testing environment (M.2412 - §8.2) targeting continuous coverage focusing on a high number of connected machine type devices.

Finally, Connection Density may be evaluated under 2 possible configurations (M.2412 - §8.4), Configuration A and B either on Uplink or Downlink. In our evaluation study, the uplink direction for configuration A has been assessed.

The parameters are detailed in the following Table.

Table 4-11 Connection Density evaluation parameters

Parameters	Urban Macro–mMTC
	Connection Density Evaluation
	Configuration A
Baseline evaluation configuration parameters	
Carrier frequency for evaluation	700 MHz
BS antenna height	25 m
Total transmit power per TRxP	46 dBm for the Operational Bandwidth (10 MHz).
UE power class	23 dBm

Percentage of high loss and low loss building type	20% high loss, 80% low loss
Additional parameters for system-level simulation	
Inter-site distance	500 m
Number of antenna elements per TRxP	8 antennas with the element patterns provided in M.2412 (MRC for reception, beamforming for unicast transmissions)
Number of UE antenna elements	2 isotropic
Device deployment	80% indoor, 20% outdoor Randomly and uniformly distributed over the area
UE mobility model	Fixed and identical speed $ v $ of all UEs of the same mobility class, randomly and uniformly distributed direction.
UE speeds of interest	3 km/h for indoor and outdoor
Inter-site interference modelling	Explicitly modelled
BS noise figure	5 dB
UE noise figure	7 dB
BS antenna element gain	8 dBi
UE antenna element gain	0 dBi
Thermal noise level	-174 dBm/Hz
Traffic model	With layer 2 PDU (Protocol Data Unit) message size of 32 bytes: 1 message/day/device or 1 message/2 hours/device Packet arrival follows Poisson arrival process for non-full buffer system-level simulation. The target was set to 1 message /2 hours / device according to the suggestion.
Simulation bandwidth	10 MHz (either as one channel)
UE density	Ten UEs per TRxP
UE antenna height	1.5 m

4.5.2 IEG Evaluation Methodology Detailing

An end-to-end event-based system and link level layer simulator for the EUHT-5G technology was developed in MATLAB by WWRF IEG, able to perform the required simulation-based evaluation campaign. The IEG developed a simulator that is able to take into account the particularities of the EUH-5G RIT, including the latest submission features, while remaining aligned with the evaluation guidelines defined in ITU-R M.2412-0. Channel modeling implementation follows M.2412 assumptions as well.

4.5.2.1 Implementation

The connection density evaluation methodology is implemented in the following steps:

Step 1: Frequency planning options are investigated based on the available number of channels and the simulation bandwidth. Given that the smallest supported bandwidth for

EUHT-5G is 5MHz and the simulation bandwidth in Configuration A is 10 MHz, there was no possibility to implement frequency reuse of 1/3 and 1/7. A single 10 MHz carrier for all TRxPs and reuse 1 are assumed.

OFDM subcarrier spacing is set to 19.53125 kHz (low frequency, low Doppler) and the size of FFT is 512. The demodulation reference signals are placed every four subcarriers and every four OFDM symbols. The twelve phase tracking pilots are repeated at every OFDM subcarriers.

Step 2: The packet to be sent is 32 bytes, i.e., 256 bits. Adding the PDU headers according to the proposal, the Cyclic Redundancy Check (CRC) suffix and applying a $\frac{1}{2}$ convolutional encoder in order to enhance reliable transmission, the total number of bits to be send is approximately 740 bits. According to the selected PHY and pilot pattern configuration, for either BPSK or QPSK modulation, two OFDM symbols per packet repetition per user should be utilized.

It is assumed that there is no traffic pattern generation process, since all 32 bytes are available to the STA at the beginning of the simulation.

Step 3: No multiplexing is performed at the uplink. Each time, all the resources are allocated to a single user (the target user for the evaluation process).

Step 4: PDU repetition is performed to enhance reliability. The effectiveness of repetitions in the reliability is evaluated. It is noted that repetitions up to four times are considered for the normal mode of operation and up to twelve times for the low-error mode of operation.

Step 5: The SINR Cumulative Density Function (CDF) distribution is extracted assuming that there is constant demand by users at all cells. Since, for the Connection Density evaluations, high congestion of users is expected, the CDF can be used to statistically generate the SINR for each user, when performing mMTC system-level simulations.

It is assumed that all neighbouring cells have allocated resources to other STAs and therefore, system-wise there are 57 interferers at a given time.

Step 6: In the analysis, the EUHT-5G frame duration was (approximately) 4 msec following the sampling period/time granularity of the simulator. This means that the time taken from the request of resources to the acknowledgement of reception at the downlink will be at least 16 msec (without taking into account the initial delays for synchronization and random access).

Step 7: TDD duplex mode is considered. The DL/UL ratio in the EUHT-5G frame dynamically changes to optimize performance. The minimum necessary slots are allocated for downlink, that carry the reference signals (e.g., DL-preamble, DL-DRS, CCH, DL-TCH), as well as the required scheduling information, and acknowledgments. It is noted that according to the described operation, a large portion is assigned to DL for each frame to carry the CCH symbols for scheduling and all responses and acknowledgments. A typical ratio for DL/UL is $\frac{1}{2}$.

Step 8: Link Level simulation is performed for the specified PHY configuration using the proposed channel model. Packet error rate curves are derived.

Step 9: The following transmission assumptions are applied:

- TRxPs with 8 antennas.
- Transmission in the uplink is based on QPSK and $\frac{1}{2}$ LDPC (MCS1) or BPSK and $\frac{1}{2}$ LDPC (MCS0) depending on the quality of the channel (as perceived by the reception of DL signals).
- Transmission in the downlink is based on:
 - BPSK and Convolutional Coding or QPSK and LDPC 3/14 for SICHs (Type I, II)
 - QPSK with LDPC 4/7 or QPSK with LDPC 3/14 for CCHs (Type I, II)
 - MCS1 or MCS0 for other signals/channels/responses contained in DL-TCH or UL-TCH.
- Sounding symbols were not used.
- Variable number of repetitions and maximum number of retransmissions (ARQ process).

Step 10: At this point, the main loop of the simulation engine can be executed.

- Ten UEs are generated per TRxP and one UE is selected for transmission at the next opportunity. The three UEs located at the central cells are assessed in terms of rate, reliability and latency. The UEs at the other cells are considered interference sources. The SINR value corresponds to the results of Step 5.
- In case of an unsuccessful transmission, then an ARQ-like process is activated (according to the EUHT-5G re-transmission strategy). The retransmission is initiated instantly, and the whole process will be prioritized at the next frame.
- Channels are generated using the IMT-2020 channel models. The channels are produced for a significantly long period to cover the possibility for a maximum number of retransmissions.

- For each retransmission, we isolate the time samples from the generated channels corresponding to the time-variant impulse responses. As far as the large-scale characteristics are concerned, for each retransmission the pathlosses are considered equal, but on the other hand, a new shadowing coefficient is generated for each retransmission.
- The packet is received correctly, if:
 - All packets exchanged to realize the process are successfully decoded (CRC check).
 - PDU repetitions utilize soft decoding, however, the demodulation and decoding attempt for each retransmission is performed independently.
- If the maximum number of retransmissions is reached, a transmission failure is marked.
- The process is repeated multiple times to estimate the achievable rate (according to the evaluation methodology in II-C-2-A-2) that relies on the average number of re-transmissions and the packet outage, i.e., the packets that are not successfully sent despite coding, repetitions, and retransmissions.
- More than 50,000 channel instances were used for the evaluation.

Figure 4-13 UL Transmission Process a) Initial steps for network joining, b) Steps for allocation of service, resources and data transmission

4.5.2.2 PHY Configuration

In the following Table, a summary of the physical layer parameters considered in the evaluation is provided.

Table 4-12 Physical Layer Parameters

Parameter	Value
Channel Bandwidth	10 MHz
Nfft	512 @ 10 MHz were tested.
Subcarrier Spacing	19.53125 kHz for the considered Nfft/BW setup
Cyclic Prefix	N/4 (normal)
Frame Structure	<p>As provided by the Proponent in Figure 69 of EUHT specifications</p> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p style="text-align: center;">FIGURE 69 General Frame Structure of physical layer</p> </div> <p>It is noted that no sounding channels were considered.</p>
Frame duration	Approximately 4 ms (62 OFDM symbols in 10MHz/512subcarriers configuration).
TDD Ratio	DL/UL ratio is set to 1/2. The UL-TCH OFDM symbols are 20.
Modulation and Coding	BPSK or QPSK. Convolutional Coding 1/3, LDPC 3/14, LDPC 1/2, LDPC 4/7 depending on the signal type and channel.
Receiver	MMSE-IRC for the first-tier neighboring stations.
MIMO	Single User MIMO With space-time coding at UL transmissions.
Repetitions	A variable number of PDU repetitions was assessed (from 1 up to 12). Soft decoding was performed utilizing the soft bits from all the repetitions.

4.5.2.3 MAC sublayer and Transmission process

For each 32-byte packet transmission, a quite significant number of steps should be completed according to the MAC specification of the EUHT-5G proposal. The process is presented in the EUHT-5G proposal (Figures 37 to 42 – summarized in Figure 1 of this evaluation). The detailed process was implemented as a 21-step procedure for the simulator. More specifically, the steps towards a successful transmission are the following:

- 1 UE Synchronization with the use of preambles.
- 2 Acquisition of SICH, CCH (broadcast), and the BCF carried in DL-TCH. Channel estimation is performed using the preambles. The BCF can be dynamically set. For our simulation, BCF is present in every frame (i.e., period 4ms).
- 3 The UE attempts to transmit a PN sequence at the UL-Random Access Channel (UL-RACH) in order to indicate its presence and eventually request services.
- 4 The TRxP (CAP), attempts to detect the random-access sequence. If multiple users select the same sequence, this will lead to a collision.
- 5 The users that experienced a collision will trigger a backoff procedure. For our simulation, no backoff at all was considered as a best-case scenario.
- 6 Assuming no collision, the TRxP will send a response acknowledging the reception (as a CCH) and will allocate resources to the UE for Random Access Request (RA-REQ).
- 7 The UE attempts to receive and decode the CCH and if it succeeds it will transmit the RA-REQ packet.
- 8 Upon RA-REQ reception, the TRxP will send a Random-Access Request Response (RA-RES) back to the UE.
- 9 Through the CCH, the TRxP will allocate resources requesting the UE basic capability set (process known as capability negotiation).
- 10 The UE will send the capability set.
- 11 The TRxP will respond on the capability negotiation
- 12 The UE will send an acknowledgment.
- 13 At the next phase, the UE will request for a service with the transmission of a dynamic service addition request frame.
- 14 The TRxP will attempt to receive the request and respond.

- 15 The UE will acknowledge.
- 16 The resource allocation request process also includes a random-access procedure. The UE sends a scheduling request sequence (randomly selected) in the UL scheduling request channel.
- 17 In case of correct reception, the TRxP will allocate resources in order to receive the scheduling request, otherwise, backoff should again be triggered.
- 18 The UE sends the scheduling request.
- 19 The resource allocation is performed.
- 20 The resources for the 32 bytes are now available to the UE, that will attempt transmission. No fragmentation is performed.
- 21 The TRxP will acknowledge correct reception. Otherwise, retransmission will be performed.

In the evaluation, only the last parts of the process is simulated (Send Dynamic Service Addition Request Frame – until the establishment of UL traffic transmission and the reception of the acknowledgement). The process is used for the evaluation of the packet outages and the calculation of the Rate for the transmission of the 32 bytes by considering the total required delay (that in this case exceeded 20 msec at best).

4.5.2.4 Error handling and failures

The process contains information exchange that is handled by the simulator (and based on the suggestions included in the proponent document) as follows:

- Synchronization is considered perfect and failure to decode SICH, CCH, or BCH at the initial stage is not considered.
- Failure during the random-access attempts is not considered.
- After a maximum number of consecutive failed transmissions by the UE (of any type), the transmission is dropped. Moreover, corresponding failure of transmission at the downlink (e.g., CCH for resource allocation, or acknowledgment of reception) will lead to a failure.
- After a maximum number of failed attempts to acquire resources (set to 8), the transmission is dropped.
- After a maximum number of retransmissions (set to variable sizes 4, 8), the MPDU is dropped.
- After 10s of unsuccessful transmission, the packet is dropped.

4.6 Results for Connection Density

4.6.1 Technical Performance

Table 4-13 Minimum technical requirement results for Connection Density

Minimum technical performance requirements (ITU-R M.2410)	Category			Required value	Value	Meets the Requirement?	Remarks
	Usage scenario	Test environment	Downlink or Uplink				
Connection density (devices/km ²)	mMTC	Urban Macro – mMTC	Uplink	1 000 000 users with less than 1% outage for a) one message per day, b) one message per 2 hours	>1 000 000 users each one transmitting one message per 24 hours, with >3% outage	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	Refer to Section 4.6.2 for further analysis

4.6.2 Observations

Connection density minimum technical performance level requires the simultaneous fulfilment of 3 conditions:

- At least 1 000 000 devices with a single 32-byte packet served over 24h
- Maximum delay of 10s
- Maximum outage probability of 1%.

Given the number of available bandwidth resources and the quite relaxed traffic volume and delay requirements, the first two conditions may be easily met. Eventually, the minimum technical performance will depend on the achieved outage level. For 10 MHz bandwidth and assuming universal frequency reuse, a 19-cell layout with 3 sectors each leads to 57 interferers per device. At 700 MHz carrier frequency the system is heavily interference limited.

Figure 4-14 An instantiation of the investigated layout. STAs from the center cell are selected as reference, while STAs from other cells are selected randomly as interferers.

System level simulation is performed to evaluate the empirical CDFs for the SINR for both uplink and downlink, since bi-directional message exchanges are required to perform the transmission. The reference SINR is calculated at the receiver assuming perfect conditions and optimal operation. Errors (e.g., channel estimation error) will further degrade these values.

Figure 4-15 Empirical CDF for the Uplink SINR – Note: calculated assuming MRC reception and perfect channel estimation.

Figure 4-16 Empirical CDF for the Downlink SINR. An uplink-limited system is considered.

Additionally, we provide the BLER curves for the Modulation and Coding schemes used during the simulation study (Figure 5). In these figures, axis x corresponds to the narrowband (per subcarrier) E_b/N_0 right prior to the application of the soft demodulator and decoder.

Figure 4-17 BLERs vs E_b/N_0 for the Modulation and Coding schemes used in the simulator

A baseline performance evaluation configuration is defined considering no repetition or re-transmission policy. On top of this we apply:

- Repetitions: A packet could be repeatedly transmitted several times, and soft LLR decoding combining the repeated packets is applied at the receiver. Repeated packets are quite close in time and channels are strongly time-correlated due to low doppler conditions.
- Re-transmissions: A failed packet is re-transmitted after 4 msec, a time interval corresponding to the packet duration for 512 subcarriers, which allows for shadowing decorrelation.

Initially, we fix the maximum number of repetitions to 4 -as defined in the EUHT-5G specs and the self-evaluation study- and investigate the outage for an increasing number of re-transmissions, up to 8. Table 3 provide the results derived for non-ideal channel estimation. Even at 8 re-transmissions, outage is higher than 1%. The process was repeated using 12 repetitions in order to assess the low-error mode operation (Table 4). However, the gain from the repetitions was not sufficient to fall below the outage threshold. Generally, the impact of repetitions is proven small, since the repeated segments practically share the exact same large-scale effects and channel characteristics. The impact of increasing the number of re-transmissions for the two repetition settings is showcased in Figure 6.

Figure 4-18 Outage Probability vs. maximum retransmission attempts for four and twelve repetitions

**Table 4-14 Outage vs ARQ Attempts
(4 repetitions)**

ARQ Attempts	Outage (%)	Minimum Requirement Fulfilment
1	24.6	No
2	11.5	No
4	6.3	No
8	3.6	No

**Table 4-15 Outage vs ARQ Attempts
(12 repetitions)**

ARQ Attempts	Outage (%)	Minimum Requirement Fulfilment
1	18.5	No
2	7.9	No
4	5.2	No
8	3.1	No

5. Conclusion

Based on the detailed observations provided, EUHT-5G does not meet the minimum criteria for both KPIs average spectral efficiency and 5th Percentile Spectral Efficiency. Only Sub 6 GHz scenarios were considered i.e., Configuration A and the candidate technology was evaluated for both DL and UL for both the KPIs. These points highlight the challenges in maintaining high spectral efficiency and reliable communication, especially for users at the cell edges and under poor channel conditions.

Also, based on the simulation-based evaluation, EUHT-5G does not meet the minimum criteria for the Connection Density KPI.

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9. List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation/Acronym	Explanation
BLER	Block Error Rate
CAP	Central Access Point
CCH	Control Channel
DL-TCH	Downlink Transmission Channel
EUHT	Enhanced Ultra High Throughput
eMBB	Enhanced Mobile Broadband
IEG	Independent Evaluation Group
IMT	Internal Mobile Telecommunications
IoT	Internet of Things
ITU	International Telecommunications Union
mMTC	Massive Machine-Type Communications
MRC	Maximum Ratio Combining
RD	Radio Device
RIT	Radio Interface Technology
RSSI	Received Signal Strength Indicator
SRIT	Set of Radio Interface Technologies
STA	Station Terminal
TCH	Transmission Channel
TRxP	Transmission-Reception Point
URLLC	Ultra-Reliable Low Latency Communications
WWRF	Wireless World Research Forum

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